

Tautomeric Pyrazolone Compounds

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In the reaction of 3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone with a number of substituted benzaldehydes, carrying electron-attracting and electron-donating groups in *ortho* and *para* positions, two tautomeric products have been obtained, one in carbonyl form and the other in enolic form. Dimethylaminobenzaldehyde under similar conditions affords, however, only one product.

The ultimate product, formed on methylation of the reaction product of 3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone with benzaldehyde, is found to be identical with that formed from benzaldehyde and antipyrine in acid medium. Aldol formation does not take place with 3,4-dimethyl-5-pyrazolone.

4-Benzylidene-5-pyrazolone has been converted into benzylidene-4,4'-bis-(5-pyrazolone) by heating with aqueous sodium carbonate solution. An attempt to prepare the above benzylidene-4,4'-bis-(5-pyrazolone), starting from benzylidene-bis-acetoacetic ester, provides a dihydropyridine compound.

Formation of aldols by the reaction of aldehydes with 5-pyrazolone and that of two tautomeric compounds by condensation of benzaldehyde with the 5-pyrazolone have been reported^{1,2}. In the present communication the reactions of substituted benzaldehydes, carrying electron-attracting and electron-donating groups in *ortho* and *para* positions, with the parent 5-pyrazolone have been studied. The different products obtained are shown in Table I.

It may be noted that whereas the first four aldehydes yield three products each, *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde furnishes the same product both in acidic and in alkaline medium.

With the hope that the compounds, 3,4-dimethyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone and antipyrine, both having only one reactive hydrogen atom in the 4-position of the pyrazolone nucleus, might form aldols on condensation with benzaldehyde, the reaction of 3,4-dimethyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone with benzaldehyde was carried out, yielding a compound, m.p. 162°. This compound could not be acetylated under any condition. The I.R. spectrum of the above compound showed no band in 2.7 μ to 3 μ region. So structure (I) is assigned to the above compound.

(I)

1. Chatterjee and Ghosh, *Proc. Asiatic Soc., Bengal*, 1910, Cxxxii, 15.
2. Mitra and Rout, *this Journal*, 1961, 38, 893.

TABLE I

R.		(A)	(B)	(C)
		Chocolate-red crystals, m.p. 173°	Pale yellow crystals, m.p. 200°	Yellowish crystals, m.p. 215°
		Bright red crystals, m.p. 112°	Colorless crystals, m.p. 200°	Colorless crystals, m.p. 230°
		Bright red crystals, m.p. 127°	Colorless crystals, m.p. 203°	Yellow crystals, m.p. 172°
		Red crystals, m.p. 23°	Pale yellow crystals, m.p. 201°	Colorless crystals, m.p. 186°
		Bright red crystals, m.p. 197°	Bright red crystals, m.p. 167°	Bright red crystals, m.p. 197°

Properties and analytical values of the compounds of structure (I), formed with different aromatic aldehydes, are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Nature of R.	M.P.	Expected.		Found.	
		%C.	%H.	%C.	%H.
Phenyl	163°	74.30	5.50	74.10	5.60
o-Nitrophenyl	90°	67.36	4.78	67.30	4.80
o-Chlorophenyl	160°	68.86	4.88	68.90	5.00

The reaction between antipyrine and benzaldehyde in presence of piperidine provided a small yield of a compound, m.p. 98-100°, and the rest of the antipyrine was recovered after the reaction. In acetic acid solution, antipyrine reacted with benzaldehyde to yield a compound, m.p. 204°. This compound was also prepared by methylation of benzylidene-4,4'-bis-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone), m.p. 203-205°, with sodium ethoxide and methyl iodide. So this product (m.p. 204°) is the *N*-methylation product of the benzylidene-4,4'-bis-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone) possessing structure (II).

Conversion of 4-benzylidene-3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone to the benzylidene-4,4'-bis-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone) by the action of piperidine has already been reported². Working with a similar molecule, 4-benzylidene-3-methyl-5-isoxazolone, Donleavy and Gilbert³ are reported to have effected a conversion to the bis-compound by treatment with an aqueous sodium carbonate solution.

It is now found that 4-benzylidene-3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone on treatment with aqueous sodium carbonate under similar conditions is converted into benzylidene-4,4'-bis-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone). It was noted² that dimethylaminobenzaldehyde condensed with the parent pyrazolone in presence of piperidine to afford benzylidene-monopyrazolone compound, whereas *p*-nitro-, *o*-chloro-, *p*-methoxy- and *p*-hydroxy-benzaldehyde condensed under the same conditions with the parent pyrazolone to provide benzylidene-bis-pyrazolone compounds. An attempt to prepare the corresponding benzylidene-bis-pyrazolone compound from 4-dimethylaminobenzylidene-3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone by treatment with aqueous sodium carbonate resulted in the formation of a red solution which on acidification afforded the unchanged dimethylaminobenzylidene-monopyrazolone. 4-Dimethylaminobenzylidene-3-methyl-5-isoxazolone on treatment with sodium carbonate did not yield the corresponding bis-compound either. So dimethylamino group in *para* position of the phenyl nucleus prevents aromatic aldehydes from forming benzylidene-bis-heterocyclic compounds with 5-pyrazolone or 5-isoxazolone.

An attempt has been made to synthesise benzylidene-4,4'-bis-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone) by an independent route.

Benzalidene-bis-acetoacetic ester was obtained in very good yield. Its reaction with phenylhydrazine did not provide the expected compound, but a compound was obtained which showed no colour reaction with ferric chloride. It has been tentatively assigned structure (III).

EXPERIMENTAL

Reaction of Aldehydes with 5-Pyrazolone—To 3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone, dissolved in minimum quantity of glacial acetic acid at room temperature, was added 1 molar proportion of the appropriate aldehyde, also in glacial acetic acid, at the room temperature. The mixture was kept at the room temperature for 12 hours and then diluted with water till turbidity appeared. After one hour red crystals of the benzylidene-monopyrazolone were collected.

The mother liquor from the above red crystals was diluted with four volumes of water when a precipitate appeared. This was filtered and crystallised twice from acetic acid to furnish the benzylidene-bis-pyrazolone in the carbonyl form.

The benzylidene-bis-pyrazolone in the enol form was obtained by condensing the appropriate aldehyde with the parent pyrazolone; on treatment with a few drops of piperidine at the room temperature, both dissolved in absolute ethanol.

TABLE III

R.	Formula.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
		Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
	C ₂₇ H ₂₃ O ₄ N ₅	67.90	87.30	5.00	4.70
	C ₂₇ H ₂₃ O ₄ N ₄ Cl	69.10	68.60	4.80	4.90
	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ O ₅ N ₄	72.65	72.10	6.00	5.50
	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ O ₅ N ₄	71.10	71.00	5.10	5.30

Methylation of Benzylidene-bis-pyrazolone.—Sodium (0.8 g.) was dissolved in super dry ethanol (25 ml) by warming. Benzylidene-4,4'-bis-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone) (enol form; m.p. 203-205°) (1g.) was added to the cooled sodium ethoxide, followed by methyl iodide (3 g.). The mixture was left in the cold for 15 minutes and then heated on a water bath for 2 hours; water (20 ml) was added to it and the ethanol was removed. The solution became neutral. A 10% NaOH solution (10 ml) was added and the alkaline mixture was extracted repeatedly with ether. The extract was dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate and the ether removed. The gummy residue after hardening with ammonium hydroxide was crystallised from acetone, m.p. 204°.

Condensation of Benzaldehyde with 3,4-Dimethyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone.—The 3,4-dimethyl-5-pyrazolone was prepared by heating together methyl ethylacetoacetate (10 ml) and phenylhydrazine (7 ml) on a water bath for 1 hour and then pouring the product on ether.

A mixture of 3,4-dimethyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone (5 g.) and benzaldehyde (3 g.) in glacial acetic acid (30 ml) was refluxed on asbestos-centred wire gauze for 2 hours. It was then cooled, water was added to it, and left overnight. The heavy liquid was washed with water by decantation and then dissolved in methanol. Needle-shaped crystals were obtained by recrystallisation from aqueous methanol, m.p. 162°. This product developed no colour with ferric chloride. It could not be acetylated with acetic anhydride and pyridine. (Found: C, 75.20; H, 6.21. $C_{25}H_{18}O_2N_4$ requires C, 75.01; H, 6.03%).

Conversion of 4-Benzylidene-3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone to Benzylidene-4,4'-bis-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone).—4-Benzylidene-3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone (5 g.) was heated at 100° on a water bath with 20% aqueous sodium carbonate solution (150 ml) for 1 hour. The reaction mixture was cooled and extracted with ether. The aqueous solution was then acidified with H_2SO_4 (dil.). The solid separating was crystallised from methanol, m.p. 161-63°. Mixed m.p. with the carbonyl form of benzylidene-4,4'-bis-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone) was not depressed. It was found that 10% aqueous NaOH solution could be used with advantage instead of sodium carbonate solution in the above conversion.

Synthesis of Benzylidene-bis-(ethyl acetoacetate).—To acetoacetic ester (10 g.) in absolute ethanol (10 ml) benzaldehyde (4 g.) was added, followed by piperidine (1 ml). The mixture was thoroughly shaken and left for 12 hours at the room temperature. A white crystalline solid was obtained which was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 150°, yield 63%.

Phenylhydrazone of Benzylidene-bis-acetoacetic Ester.—Benzylidene-bis-acetoacetic ester (5 g.) and phenylhydrazine (5 g.) were mixed together and heated on a water bath for 1 hour. It was cooled, poured into ether, and left for 1 hour. A solid crystalline product separating was filtered and washed with ether to remove coloured impurities. It was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 198-99°. It did not develop any colour with ethanolic ferric chloride solution. (Found: N, 6.35. $C_{25}H_{17}O_4N_2$ requires N, 6.50%).

Synthesis of 4-Dimethylaminobenzylidene-3-methyl-5-isoxazolone.—The oxime of *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (2 g.) was mixed with acetoacetic ester (2 g.) and orthophosphoric acid (0.4 g.) in a conical flask. Sufficient absolute ethanol was added to form a clear solution while hot. It was then refluxed on a water bath for 1 hour. On concentration and cooling, red crystals separated which were recrystallised from rectified spirit, m.p. 204°. (Found: C, 67.77; H, 5.91. $C_{13}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires C, 67.82; H, 6.08%).

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